

High-involvement work practices, quality results, and the role of HR function - an exploratory study of manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka

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Purpose- This article explores the relationship between high-involvement work practices and quality results, and the role of HR function in the implementation of quality and high-involvement work practices.

Design/methodology/approach- Quality managers and HR managers from 34 manufacturing firms with ISO 9001 certification and competing for national/international quality Awards responded. Correlation and regression were used for the data analysis.

Findings- Team work, communication, performance evaluation, empowerment, rewards and recognition, and skill development practices significantly positively correlate with quality results. Of these practices, performance evaluation has the greatest impact followed by communication, and rewards and recognition. In the implementation of quality and work practices, the role of the HR department can be identified as “steering”.

Originality/value- A majority of research studies on high-involvement work practices has been confined to Western manufacturing contexts; and findings of these studies are not conclusive. It is expected that the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data to stimulate further research in this area.

Keyword(s): High-involvement work practices, quality results, role of HR function.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

To survive and gain competitive advantage in the ever expanding and competitive global marketplace, firms have to provide quality products and services demanded by customers, delivered faster and at a lower price, through high levels of performance and commitment (Gollan, 2005; Rao *et al.*, 1999). In the circumstances, firms have identified possibilities for them to turn to continuous quality improvement concepts for increasing the efficiency of production systems and competitiveness in international as well as local markets (Raghunathan *et al.*, 1997). Continuous quality improvement is an organisation-wide process-oriented philosophy, where each employee at each level of the organisation is required to focus on his/her efforts to improve each business activity of the organisation (Mehra *et al.*, 2001).

Firms adopt high-involvement work practices (HIWPs) as part of an organisational change process, such as the implementation of quality management initiatives (Boxall and Macky, 2007; Gollan, 2005; Wall *et al.*, 1990). High-involvement work practices provide flexibility of the organisational structure entailing job enrichment, empowerment, self-managed work teams, open two-way communication, participation in decision-making, extensive skill development, reduced status differences, and rewards and recognition practices (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Edwards and Wright, 2001; Lawler, 1986). As HIWPs are intended to promote mutual influence, respect and responsibility in improving employee relations, literature on advanced manufacturing systems identifies HIWPS as the single most important contributor in assuring effective implementation of organisation improvement initiatives (Gollan *et al.*, 2005; Palo and Padhi, 2005; Shah and Ward, 2003; Yang, 2006). The literature further suggests that central to the effective implementation of quality and HIWPs is the important practitioner dimension played by the human resource (HR) function (see Murphy and Southey, 2003; Gollan, 2005).

Although HIWPs are an important dimension in contemporary research on workplaces a majority of research has been confined to Western manufacturing contexts (see Boxall and Macky, 2007). The picture is, however, unclear for Asian developing economies. Only a small number of empirical studies have explored employee involvement work practices and quality management initiatives in Asian countries, namely, Malaysia (e.g. Boon *et al.*, 2007), India (e.g. Raghunathan *et al.*, 1997), China (e.g. Sun, 2000a; Raghunathan *et al.*, 1997), and Taiwan (e.g. Chen, 1997; Yang, 2006). Therefore, there is a need to explore employee involvement work practices and quality management initiatives in different industrial sectors in different parts of the world. Such studies will provide useful information for practitioners and academics alike, and consequently, could be the basis for further research of both a qualitative and quantitative nature.

The Sri Lankan government declared a decade of productivity improvement from 1997-2006. The principles of 5-S were introduced to both private and public organisations across all sectors and encouraged them to implement these across organisations as a government initiative obtaining the involvement of several Ministries. Further, in the year 2001, the Sri

Lankan government introduced the Sri Lanka National Quality Award (SLNQA) programme. The articles in the business press and practitioner-oriented journals suggest that many manufacturing firms operating in the country are obtaining quality certifications and introducing HIWPs to workplaces. However, the situation of these manufacturing firms still remains unclear.

In the above context, the purpose of this paper is to explore 1) HIWPs used in the manufacturing firms that contribute to continuous quality improvement, and 2) the role of HR function in the implementation of quality and HIWPs. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide a better understanding of the relationship between HIWPs and quality results, and the role of HR function in Sri Lanka. Consequently, the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data to stimulate further research in this area. In order to provide the context for the article, relevant literature is briefly reviewed in the next section. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Review of literature

Quality certifications, awards, and quality results

In pursuit of total quality management, organisations use quality certification and quality awards as models for the implementation of quality initiatives (Stading and Vokurka, 2003). The implementation of quality assurance systems based on ISO 9000 standards has become a common event in the business world (Pina and Selle's, 2008). Especially, many organisations find that ISO 9000 certification is necessary to stay in business and to gain competitive advantage internationally (Pina and Selle's, 2008; Sun, 2000b). However, some criticise ISO 9000 standard as driving organisations away from contemporary quality theories and paradigms, emphasising conformance and standardisation over customer satisfaction and innovation (see Gotzamani *et al.*, 2006). Further, it is suggested that the implementation of standards cannot be considered as a sign of top management's commitment to quality, since some believe that the true motive behind certification is the certificate itself (Gotzamani *et al.*, 2006). However, many believe that standards offer a well-structured tool to start the quality

journey (see Gotzamani *et al.*, 2006; Sun, 2000b), and the possession of the certificate visibly demonstrates an organisation's commitment to worldwide quality (see Fuentes *et al.*, 2003). On the other hand, the implementation of a quality assurance system adhering to ISO 9000 standards represents a sub-system of total quality management.

Governments consider National Quality Awards (NQAs) as a means by which quality awareness can be promoted at the national level (Tan, 2002). Tan (2002) suggests that many countries have modelled their award programmes based on three key awards of Deming Prize, the European Quality Award, and the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) that have played a key role in the quality revolution in Japan, Western Europe, and the USA, respectively. For instance, the Sri Lanka National Quality Award (SLNQA) programme which was started in the year 2001 has been formulated in line with the full model of MBNQA to secure overseas recognition of Sri Lanka's quality capabilities (see Tan, 2002). However, scholars warn that simple imitation of quality standards/awards is insufficient (Gotzamani *et al.*, 2006; Sun, 2000b). On the one hand, individual organisations must judiciously tailor the criteria to fit their own individual situations (Stading and Vokurka, 2003). On the other, quality initiatives of individual organisations have to evolve from quality assurance, to process quality, quality management, and overall performance management in order to remain in touch with changing business conditions. However, research evidence shows that when quality management evolves from quality assurance, it tends to focus more on technical aspects rather than human aspects of quality (e.g. Kufidu and Vouzas, 1998; Vouzas, 2004).

The efforts of quality improvement have to be reflected in improved quality levels based on objective and subjective measures. For instance, customer satisfaction, warranty costs and complaints are external measures while the levels of defects, scrap, rework, and throughput time are internal measures (Rao *et al.*, 1999; Seth and Thripathi, 2006). Both kinds of measures enable an organisation in monitoring and controlling quality at the operational level (Rao *et al.*, 1999). After a thorough review of literature Lee and Zhou (2000) report that quality initiated organisations give the highest priority to reject and rework rate, on-time delivery, customer complaints, manufacturing lead time, material cost, direct labour and total output per

period. Further, Lee and Zhou (2000) identify on-time delivery, customer complaints, and reject and rework rate as the most popular measures among total quality initiated organisations in many countries.

High-involvement work practices

High-involvement work practices stem from the rise of high-quality production systems such as total quality management, just-in-time, and quality circles (Boxall and Macky, 2007; Co *et al.*, 1998; Forza, 1996; Hines *et al.*, 2004; Shah and Ward, 2003). High-involvement work practices have also been labelled high performance work systems (e.g. Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000), high commitment management (e.g. Wood and Albanese, 1995) and high-involvement work systems (e.g. Lawler, 1986). High-involvement work practices emphasise employee empowerment and progressive practices, for instance, in selection, training, rewards and recognition, information sharing, team-building, and socialisation. Collectively, HIWPs are designed to enhance employee and operating performance (Boxall and Macky, 2007; Womack *et al.*, 1990).

Several previous research studies sought to establish whether there is a correlation between the adoption of specific HIWPs and specific positive organisational outcomes (see Gollan *et al.*, 2005). Although findings of these studies are not conclusive they provide some evidence for correlations between certain work practices and positive organisational outcomes, such as increased organisational productivity and financial performance (see Gollan *et al.*, 2005).

High-involvement work practices are at the core of the quality philosophy and these are essential for the successful implementation of quality management programmes (see- Blackburn and Rosen, 1993; Bou and Beltran, 2005; Bowen and Lawler, 1992; Chen, 1997; Monks *et al.*, 1997; Sun *et al.*, 2000; Yang, 2006). Evidence suggests that HIWPs of employee empowerment, performance feedback, training, and communication in the quality context improve firm performance and customer satisfaction (e.g. Soltani *et al.*, 2006). Further, the literature suggests that the process-based total quality mechanism in Japan is inseparable from

team-based work practices (Yang, 1994). When team work becomes a necessity, there is a need to switch incentive systems from an individual to a group-oriented system (Mehra *et al.*, 2001). Further, Sun *et al.* (2000) found that employee involvement positively correlates with total quality management enablers and improvements in business performance. Overall, they conclude that employee involvement should be incorporated into total quality management.

Furthermore, the literature suggests that the implementation of quality management programmes change the work systems of production workers towards a high-involvement model (Wall *et al.*, 1990). Overall, lessons from this line of research have gained much importance in the literature (Boxall and Macky, 2007).

The role of human resource function

Organisational improvement efforts call for a cultural shift within the organisation by influencing dominant values, organisational structures, and the way people work together and feel about participation (Lawler, 1994). Extant literature identifies these changes to be at the heart of the HR function (Hart and Schlesinger, 1991; Monks *et al.*, 1997; Vouzas, 2004).

The importance of the HR function in the successful adoption of HIWPs has been researched in the West. For instance, Murphy and Southey (2003, p 75) suggest that “the strategic HR practitioner role of the HR function has the potential to be a pro-active agent of change with the ability to develop, plan and implement a wide variety of activities linked to firm performance”. In the context of quality management, the extent to which HR departments undertake and support change efforts has been researched (e.g. Palo and Padhi, 2005; Soltani *et al.*, 2006; Vouzas, 2004). For instance, Monks *et al.* (1997) reveal that HR department involve in foundation development, implementation, maintenance, and the evaluation of quality improvement programmes. Further, previous research provides evidence that HR professionals play a key role within the strategic management team and influence strategic and operational issues affecting TQM implementation (e.g. Hart and Schlesinger, 1991).

However, some researchers seriously question the role of the HR department in quality improvement initiatives (e.g. Vouzas, 2004). For instance, research evidence suggests that

when quality management evolves from quality assurance, the HR department's role is limited and oriented towards increasing the awareness of quality standards and handling administrative aspects of quality efforts rather than performing a strategic, high profile, change agent role (e.g. Monks *et al.*, 1997; Vouzas, 2004). Further, Monks *et al.* (1997) reveal that the responsibility for driving and steering the quality programme was generally centred at the top of the organisation, but it ranges across functions and was often not the sole responsibility of any one department. These studies highlight the importance of the HR department achieving a higher corporate status and greater decision-making authority with a more strategic orientation in implementing quality improvement initiatives (e.g. Palo and Padhi, 2005; Vouzas, 2004). Thus, in the current study, the contribution of the HR function by driving, steering and facilitating the implementation of quality management programmes and HIWPs in the manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka is explored.

Methodology

Sample

The Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka (n.d.) classifies industrial establishments into three main divisions of Mining and Quarrying; Manufacturing; and the production and distribution of Electricity, Gas and Water, as shown in Appendix I. Over 85% of the total value addition of the industrial sector comes from the manufacturing sector; the main manufacturing industries are food, beverages and tobacco; textile, wearing apparel, and leather; non-metallic mineral products; and chemicals, rubber and plastic (The Department of Census and Statistics, n.d.).

In selecting the sample, we decided to concentrate on the best performing manufacturing firms. By so doing, it is expected to establish baseline data to stimulate further research in this area. The data shown in Appendix I suggests that we have to concentrate on about one percent of the manufacturing firms (with 100 or more employees) operating in the country if we have to include firms with quality management systems and HIWPs as well as with HR departments into our sample. Therefore, the following selection criteria were used: 1)

business performance of the firms. Published secondary data, such as annual reports were used and criteria such as revenue growth and the growth of market share of the product segment were evaluated; 2) a firm should have ISO 9001 certification. ISO 9001 certification was considered as the starting place in achieving a strategic quality orientation. As detailed earlier, SLNQA is formulated in line with the full model of MBNQA. Adhering to ISO 9001 standards represents a sub-system of SLNQA, and 3) a firm should compete for national/international level quality awards at least in the past three years (refer to Table I). Of the 45 firms initially contacted and who fulfilled the criteria, 34 firms participated in the survey. Data was collected from quality managers and HR managers by means of a survey questionnaire. Section one of the questionnaire was on HIWPs and the role of the HR department. Section two was on quality results. Though this method of data collection from quality managers and HR managers has its limitations, in the absence of reliable research evidence of HIWPs, quality system performance, and the role of the HR department in quality initiatives in Sri Lanka, obtaining information from subject matter experts is considered a good starting point.

The firms that responded belong to ceramic, metal processing, wearing apparel (only for export markets in the EU and USA), polymer processing, electrical equipment, and plastic and rubber manufacturing industries. When considering the number of persons employed, 23% had 100-200 employees, 44% had 200-500 employees, 9% had 500-1000 employees, and 24% had more than 1000 employees. Other demographic details of the firms are shown in Table I.

Take in Table I

Measures

All constructs were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Cronbach's alpha reliability was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or

greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Quality results. 4-items that were commonly used in previous studies (such as Lee and Zhou, 2000; Raghunathan *et al.*, 1997) have been adopted, namely, "Customer complaints have been continually reduced during the last three years", "Number of loyal customers has increased during the last three years", "Scrap percentage has been continually reduced during the last three years", and "Rework percentage has been continually reduced during the last three years". The higher value indicates a higher level of quality results. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.859; Eigenvalue=2.834; Explained variation=70.84%.

High involvement work practices. 21-items, which were generated during the preliminary inquiries and extant literature (such as Blackburn and Rosen, 1993; Bou and Beltran, 2005; Lawler, 1994; Rao *et al.*, 1999; Sun *et al.*, 2000) were used to evaluate team work, skill development, empowerment, rewards and recognition, performance evaluation, and communication. 21-item measure had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.945. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of six factors, which explained 74% (74.15) of the variance. The results suggest that 21-item scale clearly fall within six groups describing different dimensions of HIWPs proposed for the study. Further, every indicator corresponds to the dimension that this indicator was assumed to measure. Table II summarises the results of factor analysis.

Take in Table II

Role of HR function. HR department's involvement in the implementation of quality and HIWPs along with other key players (CEO/Board of Directors, Quality department, and Production

department) was adapted from Monks *et al.* (1997). The level of involvement was measured on a scale of driving, steering and facilitating.

Results

Descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations of the variables are shown in table III. Team work, communication, performance evaluation, empowerment, rewards and recognition, and skill development practices significantly positively correlate with quality results.

Take in Table III

The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table IV. The model explains 89% of the variance in the quality results (Adj. $R^2 = 0.894$, $p < 0.001$). High-involvement work practices have significant positive impact on quality results. Performance evaluation has the greatest impact ($\beta = .826$, $p < 0.001$) followed by communication ($\beta = .399$, $p < 0.01$) and rewards and recognition ($\beta = .339$, $p < 0.01$).

Take in Table IV

The role of the HR function and other key players in the implementation of quality and HIWPs are shown in Table V. The role of the HR department can be mainly identified as “steering” (70%). With regard to the role of other key players, the CEO/Board of Directors (56%) and the production department (74%) mainly involve in “driving” the initiatives while the quality department (59%) and general administration (58%) mainly involve in “steering” the initiatives.

Take in Table V

Conclusions and implications

The main intention of the study was to explore HIWPs, quality results, and the role of the HR function in the implementation of quality and HIWPs. Drawing from past research (such as Lee and Zhou, 2000; Raghunathan *et al.*, 1997), quality results were measured by the reduction in customer complaints, increase in number of customers, and decrease in scrap and rework percentages. The results suggest that firms achieved considerably high levels of quality results (Table III). Drawing from past research (such as Gollan *et al.*, 2005; Sun *et al.*, 2000; Yang, 2006) six HIWPs were explored, i.e., team work, skill development, empowerment, rewards and recognition, performance evaluation, and communication. The results suggest a considerable level of implementation of these practices (Table III).

All the six HIWPs have a significant positive effect on quality results, suggesting that organisations with a higher level of work practices score higher on quality results. Of these practices, performance evaluation, communication, and rewards and recognition have the greatest influence. Overall, the findings support the claims made by past researchers that specific HIWPs may result in specific positive organisational outcomes (e.g. Boxall and Macky, 2007; Gollan *et al.*, 2005), and in the case of our study, quality results.

With regard to the role of the HR function in the implementation of quality and HIWPs, a majority of the firms (70%) identify the role as “steering”. Some past studies (e.g. Monks *et al.*, 1997; Soltani *et al.*, 2006) also investigated the role of the HR department in quality management initiatives. For instance, Soltani *et al.* (2006) revealed that 61% of firms in their study identified the role of the HR department as driving and steering in appraising employee performance. Further, Monks *et al.* (1997) reported that less than half of the firms in their study could be described as very involved while approximately 15% of HR departments were excluded completely from the development and implementation of quality initiatives.

As very little work has been directed towards the relationship between HIWPs and quality results, the findings of our exploratory study open the door for further investigations. For instance, findings suggest that practices adopted by firms lead to quality communication and consultation between management and employees. However, investigating the ways in which,

for instance, jobs are designed to be broader and teams made accountable for performance are beyond the scope of our study. Further, we have not explored whether ISO 9000 certification has provided the building blocks for successful implementation of continuous quality management systems and that HIWPs have been introduced as part of the implementation of continuous quality management systems. It would be of interest, therefore, to identify reasons behind the adoption of HIWPs. Furthermore, future studies could investigate the ways in which HR departments are involved in, for instance, in formulating quality friendly policies, generating quality awareness among employees, overcoming communication barriers, redesigning work processes, managing the psychological transition, and motivating employees to achieve total quality.

One of the major limitations of this study is the small sample size. However, as an exploratory study a large sample may not necessarily add significant knowledge. However, if the sample size was larger, path analysis could have been used to investigate interrelations among variables. Further, for the study, data was collected from quality managers' and HR managers' points of view. This limitation can be overcome by obtaining employees' and line managers' perceptions of the same. This may lead to identify any differences in the perceptions of different parties involved in the process. Furthermore, although the study was designed to be exploratory in nature, we adopted a survey-based approach. Therefore, future studies could adopt a more qualitative approach and complement the questionnaire survey with interviews and secondary data.

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Tables

Table I: Characteristics of the sample

	F	%
Certifications obtained [‡] :		
ISO 9001	34	100
ISO 14001	11	32
Other [such as Worldwide Responsible Apparel Production (WRAP), Ethical Trading Initiatives (ETI) & Global Sourcing Principles (GSP)]	19	56
Awards won [‡] :		
National Quality Award (SLNQA)	2	6
National Productivity Award	2	6
National 5S Award	4	12
Other National Level Awards (such as National Safety Award, National Business Excellence Award, National HRM Award)	27	79
International level Awards (such as Willis Carroon International Award for Risk Management, Taiki Akimoto Award for 5S Productivity Techniques)	13	38
Percentage of annual revenue from exports:		
None (supplying only for the local market)	10	29
Less than 10%	7	21
10% - 40%	3	9
40% - 75%	2	6
More than 75%	12	35
Number of people in HR Department [†]		
Less than 3	1	3
3-5	14	41
5-10	12	35
More than 10	7	21
Number of people in Quality Department [†]		
Less than 3	1	3
3-5	5	15
5-10	17	50
More than 10	11	32

Notes: [‡] = Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple responses

[†] = All firms had a separate department

Table II: Factor analysis- HIWPs

	F1: Team work	F2: Skill development	F3: Communication	F4: Performance and evaluation	F5: Rewards and recognition	F6: Empowerment
Employees actively involve in team-based activities	.807					
Employees trust that team effort drive high performance	.785					
Employees willingly contribute to team work	.777					
A proper system is implemented to identify training requirements		.859				
Targets on employee skill development have been achieved during the last three years		.792				
Training hours allocated per employee have been increased during the last three years.		.728				
Number of training opportunities provided per employee has increased during the last three years		.720				
Precise information is communicated on time			.856			
Clear and understandable information is communicated on time.			.810			
Information available is relevant to be acted upon on time			.780			
Accurate information is communicated on time			.727			
The performance appraisal system has been continually improved during the last three years				.874		
The performance appraisal system is linked to key performance indicators				.828		
The performance appraisal system covers all possible areas of work				.728		
The rewards and recognition system covers all possible areas of work					.875	
The rewards and recognition system has been continually improved during the last three years					.842	
The rewards and recognition system stimulates employee commitment to organisational improvement efforts					.760	
Employees willingly accept responsibilities						.861
All employee suggestions are evaluated after collection						.826
The system encourages employees to give suggestions						.801
Employees are given required authority to implement suggestions						.734
Explained variation	28.51	14.32	10.16	9.32	7.44	4.40
Eigenvalue	6.92	3.01	2.52	2.20	1.78	1.05
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.794	.833	.804	.842	.794	.810

Table III: Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Team work	3.65	.52	1					
2. Skill development	3.74	.59	.490**	1				
3. Communication	3.77	.51	.336**	.340**	1			
4. Performance evaluation	3.84	.60	.310**	.326**	.474**	1		
5. Rewards and recognition	3.57	.72	.455**	.394**	.394**	.339**	1	
6. Empowerment	4.03	.59	.375**	.450**	.359**	.365**	.378*	1
7. Quality results	3.84	.71	.799**	.527**	.847**	.897**	.581**	.456**

Note: ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table IV: Regression results

	β
Team work	.249*
Skill development	.289*
Communication	.399**
Performance evaluation	.826***
Rewards and recognition	.339**
Empowerment	.266*
Model R ² (Adj.)	.894***

Note: ***p< .001, **p< .01, *p< .05.

Table V: Role of HR function and other key players

	Driving (%)	Steering (%)	Facilitating (%)	Summary: Main role
CEO/Board of Directors	55.89	26.50	23.50	Driving
Quality department	11.76	58.84	25.90	Steering
Production department	73.54	5.88	--	Driving
General administration	18.20	57.58	24.24	Steering
HR department	18.18	69.70	21.92	Steering

Note: Percentages do not add up to 100 due to multiple responses

Appendix I: Industrial establishments (as at 2004)

Division	Establishments [†]			Persons engaged ^{††}						
	Total	Small [‡]	Medium and large ^{‡‡}	Total		Small [‡]		Medium and large ^{‡‡}		
	F	F	%	F	%	F	F	%	F	%
Mining and Quarrying	6,248	5,413	4.5	835	8.4	36,948	21,378	7.5	15,570	2.1
Manufacturing[◊]	124,351	115,351	95.0	9,000	90.3	990,348	262,716	92.0	727,632	97.3
Electricity, Gas and Water	788	657	0.5	131	1.3	6,155	1,453	0.5	4,702	0.6
Total	131,387	121,421	100	9,966	100	1,033,451	285,547	100	747,904	100

Manufacturing industry[◊]

size class of persons engaged ^{††}	Establishments [†]		Persons engaged ^{††}		
	F	%	F	%	
Small [‡]	1-4	104,046	33.7	192,859	19.5
	5-9	11,305	3.1	39,859	7.1
	Subtotal	115,351		262,716	
Medium and large ^{‡‡}	10-19	1,316	3.5	55,676	5.6
	20-49	2,239	1.8	36,270	3.7
	50-99	1,043	0.8	39,986	7.1
	100 and above	1,402	1.1	535,700	54.1
	Subtotal	3,000		727,632	
Total	124,351	100	990,348	100	

Notes:

[†] Establishment characteristics- Availability of its own production facilities, distinct management and a suitable location, and maintaining of accounts.

^{††} Number of persons engaged includes working proprietors, active partners, unpaid family workers, operatives and all other employees.

[‡] Less than 10 persons engaged

^{‡‡} 10 and more persons engaged.

[◊] Manufacturing establishment: Conversion of something or part into another by using chemical or mechanical processes.

Source: Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka (n.d.)